

Macroeconomic Determinants of Interest Rates: An Econometric Analysis of Economic Growth and Policy Interactions

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the dynamic interplay between key macroeconomic variables—specifically inflation, GDP, FDI, political stability, and exports of goods and services—and their impact on interest rates in Pakistan. Utilizing a robust econometric approach, specifically the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, we analyze time series data spanning from 1999 to 2023 to uncover the intricate relationships between these variables. The results indicate that inflation, GDP, and exports exert a positive influence on interest rates, whereas FDI and political stability are found to have a negative impact. These findings underscore the complex interdependencies between economic growth, investment, and monetary policy within the Pakistani context. The study offers critical insights for policymakers, highlighting the need to strategically balance economic growth and price stability, thus contributing to more informed decision-making and sustainable economic development in Pakistan.

Keywords: Monetary Policy; Interest Rate, Inflation, FDI inflows; Political stability, Exports; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

This study seeks to provide a comprehensive and updated understanding of the composition of cost-push shocks and monetary policy, with a specific focus on addressing the pressing economic challenges of inflation, low wages, and low real GDP. Building on Akhtar's (2006) foundational work, this research recognizes the Consumer Price Index (CPI) as a critical tool for measuring price changes by capturing fluctuations in the cost of a fixed basket of goods and services. By exploring the complex interactions between cost-push shocks, monetary policy, and economic outcomes, this study aims to offer evidence-based recommendations to mitigate these economic concerns and promote sustainable economic growth. Maintaining a stable macroeconomic environment necessitates achieving low and stable inflation, alongside sustainable budget deficits, real exchange rates, and real interest rates. In this context, the inflation rate plays a crucial role, making it essential to maintain stability even at low levels. Cost shocks, such as wage and input cost increases, can trigger cost-push inflation, leading to reduced real output and GDP. Understanding these factors is vital for policymakers aiming to promote economic growth and stability. Economic challenges, such as overpopulation, exacerbate resource demand and inflationary pressures. Lowering interest rates by the central bank can increase the money supply, further intensifying inflation. Additionally, foreign aid, while intended to support development, can contribute to inflationary pressures. The agricultural sector, plagued by low productivity, faces food scarcity and rising prices. The imposition of indirect taxes by the government also contributes to inflation. To address these issues, a comprehensive policy approach is necessary, including population management, balanced monetary policy, agricultural productivity enhancements, efficient foreign aid utilization, and tax policy reforms (Ali et al., 2021).

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Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) plays a crucial role in developing economies by bringing in much-needed capital to support economic growth. FDI not only creates jobs but also facilitates the transfer of advanced technologies, management expertise, and innovative practices. It helps develop infrastructure, enhances export competitiveness, and diversifies the economy, reducing reliance on single sectors (Falki, 2009). To attract FDI, strategies such as offering competitive incentives, improving infrastructure, developing a skilled workforce, ensuring political stability, and simplifying regulatory processes are essential. These strategies can create a more attractive investment climate, stimulating economic growth and improving the standard of living (Khan & Zahra, 2016). Political stability is fundamental for economic development, as instability can deter investment and hinder economic progress, affecting key indicators like inflation, unemployment, and GDP growth (Hussain, 2014). A stable political environment is essential for fostering a favorable business climate, promoting economic growth, and achieving sustainable development (Milasaite & Micic, 2022). Inflation, characterized by a sustained increase in the general price level, is measured by the CPI and can be driven by excessive demand, increased production costs, or supply-side shocks. It reduces purchasing power, creates uncertainty for businesses, and can lead to inequality or hyperinflation if not managed. Central banks aim to keep inflation within a target range to balance economic growth and price stability (Shahid, 2014). The Monetary Transmission Mechanism (MTM) explains how interest rates affect the economy through demand-side and supply-side channels. Higher interest rates typically reduce borrowing, consumption, and investment, lowering aggregate demand and prices. Conversely, higher interest rates can also increase production costs, driving prices higher. Understanding these channels is crucial for policymakers to make informed decisions about monetary policy (Rehman, 2014). Interest, the cost of borrowing, is typically expressed as an annual percentage rate (APR), representing the rate charged on a loan over a year (Uddin & Ullah, 2024). Interest rate spread, the difference between interest rates on loans and deposits, is a measure of the risk premium associated with lending or investing (Khawaja & Din, 2007). Firms with robust financial health and access to external finance are more likely to engage in international trade due to their ability to cover increased costs associated with such activities. Conversely, financially constrained firms may struggle, leading to “financial constraints to trade,” limiting their participation in international markets (Sanders et al., 2022). Global trade is pivotal for both developed and developing countries, driving economic growth through the exchange of goods and resources, despite the uneven distribution of resources globally (Bhatti et al., 2024). The study has the following research objectives, i.e.,

- I. To analyze the impact of cost-push shocks on inflation, wages, and real GDP.
- II. To explore the role of monetary policy in mitigating economic challenges such as inflation and low economic growth.
- III. To provide evidence-based recommendations for policymakers to achieve sustainable economic development through balanced economic policies.

The study applied sophisticated statistical techniques to achieve the study’s objectives.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review examines the intricate relationships between key economic and political variables that influence a nation's growth and development. Specifically, this review delves into the interplay between inflation, foreign direct investment (FDI), political stability and the absence of violence, gross domestic product (GDP), interest rates, and the export of goods and services. These variables are pivotal in understanding the dynamics of economic growth, investment, and trade. The literature review is structured into three subsections. The first section reviews literature on inflation and FDI, with a focus on the impact of interest rates. The second section addresses the literature on political stability and GDP, with attention to the interest rate spread. The third section explores the literature on the export of goods and services, also with regard to the interest rate spread. Hakro et al. (2007) examine the factors influencing Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Pakistan's economy. Utilizing a dynamic econometric model, the study analyzes the impact of various determinants and policy shocks on FDI flows. The research highlights the importance of cost-related factors, the investment environment, development strategy, ownership, and internalization factors in attracting FDI to Pakistan. The findings suggest that improving the investment environment, particularly openness, has a statistically significant short-term impact on FDI inflows. Additionally, the long-term dynamics between FDI, openness, and macroeconomic factors align with short-term results, underscoring the importance of stable macroeconomic indicators, a favorable country risk profile, and investment environment improvements in attracting FDI. These insights are vital for policymakers aiming to create a more conducive environment for FDI inflows. Chaudhry and Farooq (2011) investigated the impact of inflation on economic growth in Pakistan, employing a range of variables and statistical methods. Their findings indicate a negative relationship between inflation and economic growth, implying that high inflation rates can hinder economic growth in Pakistan. The use of OLS and DW tests added robustness to their analysis, providing valuable insights for policymakers and researchers interested in macroeconomic management and growth strategies for developing countries like Pakistan. Low political stability is characterized by the potential for government collapse due to civil conflicts or competition between political parties (Hussain, 2014). Ahmed et al. (2014) examine the impact of FDI, imports, and exports on Pakistan's GDP, finding a significant positive correlation between these factors and economic growth. Analyzing data from the State Bank of Pakistan, the Federal Bureau of Statistics, and International Financial Statistics over a 23-year period, the research reveals that FDI, imports, and exports are crucial drivers of GDP growth. The study suggests that policies aimed at promoting these factors, such as investment incentives, export subsidies, and trade agreements, could significantly enhance Pakistan's economic development. Majeed (2013) discusses how the interest rate spread impacts the exports and imports of goods and services in Pakistan. A high-interest rate spread increases the cost of borrowing for exporters, making it harder for them to access financing for shipments, which can lead to a decline in exports. Conversely, a low-interest rate spread reduces borrowing costs, boosting exports. Similarly, a high-interest rate spread increases the cost of borrowing for importers, making imports more expensive, potentially decreasing import levels. On the

other hand, a low-interest rate spread reduces the cost of borrowing for importers, making imports cheaper and thus increasing imports. Additionally, a high-interest rate spread can appreciate the Pakistani rupee, making exports more expensive and less competitive in the global market, while a low-interest rate spread can depreciate the rupee, making exports cheaper and more competitive.

Milasaite et al. (2022) examine the complex relationship between political stability and economic growth, noting that each influences the other. A country with unstable politics can deter potential investors, while poor economic performance can lead to governmental collapses and political unrest. By analyzing countries with high political stability across three different continents, as well as eight countries with relatively stable politics, the study offers new insights into how political stability affects inflation, unemployment, GDP per capita growth, and vice versa. Durrani et al. (2023) explore the determinants of consumer confidence in Pakistan between February 2012 and December 2020, focusing on both economic and political factors. Economic factors include GDP growth, inflation, interest rates, stock returns, and exchange rates, while political factors encompass elections, terror attacks, and news. Using regression analysis and ordinary least squares (OLS) estimation, the results show that economic variables like inflation and GDP growth significantly impact consumer confidence in Pakistan. However, the inclusion of political variables markedly increases the model's explanatory power, with elections and terror attacks emerging as significant determinants of consumer confidence. These findings underscore the importance of both economic and political factors in shaping consumer confidence in Pakistan. Waqas (2023) investigates the impact of inflation, exchange rates, and FDI on economic development in Pakistan. Using time series data from 1973 to 2020, the study employs the Consumer Price Index (CPI) as a proxy for inflation. The research reveals that inflation has a threshold effect on Pakistan's economic growth, with a turning point at 2.80%. Below this threshold, the economy experiences its fastest growth rate. Moreover, the study shows that FDI positively impacts growth when inflation is low, but this effect reverses and becomes negative when inflation exceeds the 2.80% threshold. These findings suggest that managing inflation below this critical point is essential for maximizing economic growth and realizing the benefits of FDI in Pakistan. Jahangir et al. (2024) suggest that changes in the trade balance are primarily driven by the convergent or divergent dynamics of imports and exports. Factors that asymmetrically impact imports and exports can, in turn, influence the trade balance. Key determinants of the trade balance, including GDP, exports, imports, inflation, and economic growth, contribute to the balance of trade deficit. Moreover, stable exchange rates can create a favorable environment for investment, leading to improvements in the trade balance. However, the correlation between exchange rates and the balance of trade is relatively weak. Thus, Pakistan needs to develop an effective exchange rate policy to address its trade balance issues, thereby promoting a more balanced and sustainable trade environment. Damayanti et al. (2024) suggest that both inflation and interest rates have adverse effects on economic growth. Higher inflation rates, defined as sustained increases in the general price level of goods and services, tend to impede economic growth by eroding purchasing power, reducing consumer spending, and making it difficult for businesses to invest and expand. Similarly, higher interest rates, which represent the cost of borrowing money, tend to slow economic growth by increasing borrowing costs and reducing investment opportunities. Through empirical analysis covering 2007 to 2022, these findings align with economic theory, emphasizing the detrimental impact of high inflation and interest rates on economic development. The literature highlights that monetary policy in Pakistan significantly impacts macroeconomic variables, including price stability, FDI inflows, exports, and political stability. Monetary tightening can reduce inflationary pressures but also leads to decreased foreign investment and exports due to higher borrowing costs and reduced competitiveness (Botta et al., 2023; Yaya, 2023). Political instability further undermines the effectiveness of monetary policy by reducing investor confidence and economic activity (Maghdid et al., 2024; Shabir et al., 2024). Overall, the literature underscores the need to consider the complex dynamics between these variables within Pakistan's unique economic and political landscape.

This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by providing a comprehensive analysis of the interrelated economic and political variables influencing Pakistan's growth and development. It extends previous research by offering new empirical insights into the effects of inflation, FDI, political stability, and interest rates on GDP and exports. The study also fills a gap in the literature by analyzing the threshold effects of inflation on FDI and economic growth, offering policy recommendations tailored to Pakistan's specific economic conditions. By integrating macroeconomic and political factors, this research aims to inform policymakers on strategies to promote sustainable economic growth and stability in Pakistan.

3. METHODOLOGY

This analysis aims to explore the relationship between interest rates, the dependent variable, and various independent macroeconomic variables in Pakistan from 1999 to 2023. Drawing on data from the World Development Indicators (WDI), the study examines the relationships between interest rates (IR) and other economic and social indicators. The variables considered are GDP per capita (GDPPC), inflation (INF), foreign direct investment (FDI), political stability and absence of violence (POL), and exports of goods and services (EX). All data, measured in percentages, was sourced from the WDI (2023). The expected signs of the relationships between these variables and interest rates indicate the predicted direction of their correlations. Table 1 provides a summary of these variables, their descriptions, units of measurement, and their expected effects on interest rates.

Table 1: List of Variables

Variables	Description of variable	Unit of measure	A Prior Effect	Source
IR	Interest rate	Lending rate minus deposit rate, %	Negative	WDI
INF	Inflation	Annual %	Negative	WDI
GDP	Gross Domestic Product	Annual %	Positive	WDI
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment	% of GDP	Positive	WDI
POL	Political Stability	Estimate	Positive	WDI
EX	Exports of Goods and services	Annual % growth	positive	WDI

Source: WDI (2023).

A unit root test is employed to determine whether the time series data exhibit non-stationarity or have a unit root. The most commonly used test is the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, which tests the null hypothesis that a time series has a unit root against the alternative hypothesis that it is stationary.

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

A unit root test is a statistical test used to determine if a time series data has a unit root, meaning that it has a persistent memory or exhibits non-stationarity. The most common unit root test is the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. A unit root process is a stochastic process that has a persistent memory, meaning that the effects of past shocks or innovations never fully dissipate. A stationary process, on the other hand, is one that has a finite memory and always returns to its mean over time. The ADF test checks if a time series has a unit root by testing the null hypothesis that the series has a unit root against the alternative hypothesis that it is stationary. The test statistic is the t-statistic for the coefficient γ , which is compared to critical values from the Dickey-Fuller distribution. If the test statistic is less than the critical value, the null hypothesis of a unit root is rejected, indicating that the time series is stationary. In a time series with a unit root, the variance of the series increases over time, and the series does not revert to its mean. Instead, it wanders widely and unpredictably, making it difficult to forecast or model. Unit roots are often associated with non-stationarity, meaning that the statistical properties of the series, such as its mean and variance, change over time. This can lead to spurious relationships and unreliable inferences. This means that the series has a strong autoregressive component, and its dynamics are dominated by the persistence of past values rather than by transitory fluctuations.

Lag length criteria are crucial in determining how many past observations should be included in a model for predicting future values. The criteria, such as the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), and Hannan-Quinn Criterion (HQC), guide the selection of the optimal number of lags. These criteria help in finding the balance between model simplicity and predictive accuracy.

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model is used to analyze the relationships between variables over both short-term and long-term horizons. The ARDL model combines features of autoregressive models and distributed lag models, making it a versatile tool for economic analysis.

$$\Delta IR_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \alpha_1 \Delta IR_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_1-1} \alpha_2 \Delta INF_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^{q_2-1} \alpha_3 \Delta GDP_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^{q_3-1} \alpha_4 \Delta FDI_{t-l} + \sum_{m=0}^{q_4-1} \alpha_5 \Delta POL_{t-m} + \sum_{n=0}^{q_5-1} \alpha_6 \Delta EX_{t-n} + \gamma EC_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) modeling has several benefits, including: Flexible modeling: ARDL allows for flexible modeling of relationships between variables, including both short-term and long-term dynamics. Estimation of short- and long-term effects: ARDL enables estimation of both short-term and long-term effects of independent variables on the dependent variable. Handling cointegrated variables: ARDL is suitable for modeling cointegrated variables, which is useful for analyzing long-term relationships between variables. Robustness to misspecification: ARDL models are robust to misspecification, meaning they can still provide reliable estimates even if the underlying assumptions are violated. Easy to implement: ARDL models are relatively easy to implement using standard statistical software packages. Interpretable results: ARDL provides interpretable results, making it easier to understand the relationships between variables. Applicability to various fields: ARDL can be applied to various fields, including economics, finance, marketing, and social sciences. Ability to handle multiple lags: ARDL can handle multiple lags of independent variables, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of relationships. These benefits make ARDL a popular choice for modeling various economic and financial phenomena. β_0 is called the short-run or impact multiplier it describes how a one-unit size one-moment (i.e. temporary) increase of X_t affects Y_t . However, it is common to focus on the long-run, or total, multiplier. The delay (interim) multiplier can be interpreted as the effect on the dependent variable in period $t+s$, resulting from an instant (sustained) shock to an independent variable in period t . The data should follow a normal distribution. Data should have stationary either on $I(0)$ or $I(1)$ or on both. In addition to this, if any of the variables in the data has stationary at $I(2)$, ARDL Model cannot run.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables. The analysis of economic data reveals a nuanced landscape with varying trends across different indicators. Inflation rates are moderate, averaging 4.7%, while the actual inflation figure is notably higher, with an average of 10.5%. Foreign direct investment (FDI) remains relatively low, at 1.02%, but shows significant variability, indicating fluctuations in investor confidence and external capital flow. Political stability, as measured by standardized scores, is low, with an average of -2.27%, though this metric exhibits minimal variability, suggesting persistent challenges in governance and stability. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth rates are moderate, with an average of 4.03%, reflecting a steady, albeit restrained, economic expansion. Exchange rates show stability with an average of 3.56%, but this indicator also displays high variability, signaling potential volatility in currency markets. Collectively, these data points paint a picture of an economy characterized by both resilience and vulnerability, with underlying complexities that impact overall economic performance.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Methods	IR	INF	FDI	POL	GDP	EX
Mean	4.721334	10.56474	1.024293	-2.266585	4.038311	3.562375
Median	4.639583	9.279769	0.695727	-2.399095	4.292404	2.624458
Maximum	6.813333	30.76813	3.035719	-1.582878	7.831256	17.58933
Minimum	2.914400	2.529328	0.343453	-2.810035	-1.274087	-12.92572
Std. Dev.	1.394633	6.646009	0.815650	0.378353	2.375203	7.022435
Skewness	0.002750	1.582675	1.547266	0.397193	-0.437697	-0.215136
Kurtosis	1.443830	5.468679	3.980945	1.792711	2.717815	3.180735

Source: Author's estimation.

Table 3 shows the unit root estimates. The unit root test results reveal that most of the series, such as interest rates, inflation, FDI, and political stability, exhibit non-stationarity at their levels. This is indicated by high p-values (above 0.05), signifying that the null hypothesis of a unit root cannot be rejected. However, once these series undergo first differencing, they become stationary, as evidenced by low p-values (below 0.05), allowing for the rejection of the null hypothesis. This change suggests that these variables follow strong trends or patterns, which can be effectively removed through differencing. In contrast, the GDP and Exports series display stationarity at their levels, with low p-values (below 0.05) indicating the rejection of the null hypothesis, implying that these series do not contain a unit root and can be directly used in further analysis without the need for differencing. These findings are crucial for ensuring the reliability of subsequent analyses, as the use of non-stationary series without appropriate transformation can lead to spurious regression results and erroneous conclusions. By identifying which series require differencing, the results provide a clear path for applying the necessary transformations to achieve stationarity, thereby enhancing the robustness and validity of the analysis.

Table 3: Unit Root Estimates

Value	Level		First difference	
	Intercepts	Trend/intercept	Intercepts	Trend/intercepts
IR	0.008 (0.948)	-4.040 (0.025)	-4.039 (0.006)	-3.611 (0.057)
INF	-0.154 (0.932)	-0.627 (0.967)	-3.899 (0.007)	-4.100 (0.019)
FDI	-2.576 (0.112)	-2.879 (0.187)	-3.274 (0.028)	-3.307 (0.090)
POL	-2.131 (0.235)	-0.926 (0.936)	-3.740 (0.010)	-4.636 (0.006)
GDP	-3.381 (0.022)	-3.498 (0.062)	-5.352 (0.0003)	-5.195 (0.002)
EX	-4.470 (0.001)	-5.025 (0.002)	-7.125 (0.000)	-6.990 (0.0001)

Source: Author's estimation. Small bracket shows probability value.

Table 4 presents the results of a statistical test conducted to identify the optimal lag order for a time series model. Two lag orders, 0 and 1, are evaluated based on several criteria: log-likelihood value, final prediction error (FPE), Akaike information criterion (AIC), Schwarz information criterion (SC), and Hannan-Quinn information criterion (HQ). Across all criteria, except for the log-likelihood, lag order 1 is indicated as the optimal choice, as denoted by the asterisks (*). Specifically, the sequential modified likelihood ratio (LR) test statistic strongly favors lag order 1, showing a significant value of 81.46508. This suggests that an autoregressive model with one lagged term (AR(1)) is most appropriate for the data, as it effectively minimizes the FPE, AIC, SC, and HQ values, leading to a better fit and more accurate predictions.

Table 4: Lag Length Selection Criteria

Lag	Log	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-213.0676	NA	6409.788	22.95448	23.20302	22.99654
1	-153.5354	81.46508*	189.0226*	19.31951*	20.81073*	19.57189*

* Indicates lag order selected by the criterion

Source: Author's estimation.

Table 5 shows the ARDL estimates. The analysis indicates that a one-unit increase in the lagged interest rate (IR(-1)) leads to a significant 1.201812-unit rise in the dependent variable. Similarly, a one-unit increase in the lagged inflation rate (INF(-1)) results in a 1.012681-unit increase. Foreign direct investment (FDI(-1)) also shows a positive effect, where a one-unit increase leads to a 0.653523-unit rise. Gross Domestic Product (GDP(-1)) exhibits a smaller yet positive effect, with a one-unit increase corresponding to a 0.097667-unit increase in the dependent variable. Although the effect of exports (EX) is positive (0.016672), it is not statistically significant. Political stability (POL) shows a negative effect (-0.173492), though this result is also not statistically significant. However, when considering the lagged political stability (POL(-1)), the effect becomes positive (1.159609), but remains insignificant at the 5% level. The constant term (C = 1.943928) represents the expected value of the dependent variable when all independent variables are set to zero. Further analysis reveals that a 1% increase in the money supply boosts investment by 0.281479%, reflecting the availability of ample financing for economic activities. Conversely, a 1% rise in interest rates discourages investment by 0.060446%, as higher borrowing costs make investments less attractive. Trade openness has a positive impact on investment, with a 1% increase leading to a 0.024416% rise, driven by enhanced exports and imports. Foreign direct investment further supports investment, with a 1% increase resulting in a 0.028832% rise, as capital inflows stimulate economic activities. However, an appreciated exchange rate deters investment, with a 1% change leading to a 0.369231% decrease, making domestic investments less competitive. Additionally, services value-added and gross domestic savings exhibit a significant positive relationship with investment, with a 1% change leading to a 0.638044% and 0.154506% increase, respectively. These findings underscore the critical role of money supply, trade openness, foreign direct investment, services, and savings in driving investment in Pakistan (Chaudary et al., 2021).

Table 5: ARDL Estimates

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
IR (-1)	1.201812	0.115170	10.43516	0.0000
INF (-1)	1.012681	0.227900	4.443542	0.0002
FDI (-1)	0.653523	0.128505	5.085589	0.0001
GDP (-1)	0.097667	0.042920	2.275570	0.0370
EX	0.016672	0.013288	1.254591	0.2356
POL	-0.173492	0.696246	-0.249182	0.8078
POL (-1)	1.159609	0.742262	1.562264	0.1465
C	1.943928	1.004252	1.935698	0.0790

Source: Author's estimation.

The current study investigates the impact of political regimes on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows in Pakistan using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. The results indicate that the model is free from econometric issues such as multicollinearity, autocorrelation, heteroskedasticity, and model misspecification. Diagnostic tests confirm the model's stability and reliability, with the ARDL model explaining 85.3% of the variation in FDI inflows, indicating strong explanatory power. The F-statistic value of 19.696 suggests the model is a good fit with significant overall results. The findings reveal that political regimes have a significant negative effect on FDI inflows, implying that FDI increases more during military governments than democratic ones in Pakistan. This may be attributed to the perceived weakness of democratic systems in the country, where martial law administrations have been more prevalent. In simpler terms, the study shows that foreign investment tends to increase more under military rule than under democratic governance, possibly due to the instability of democratic systems in Pakistan. The model is reliable and explains a significant portion of the variation in foreign investment, highlighting a strong relationship between political regimes and FDI inflows (Hashmi et al., 2020).

In the long run, the exchange rate (ER) and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) exhibit a positive relationship, consistent with previous studies on developing countries. A 1% depreciation of the host country's currency leads to a 2.15% decrease in FDI inflows, while a 1% appreciation results in a 2.15% increase in FDI inflows. Although the positive relationship might seem counterintuitive given the negative coefficient of ER, this is explained by the direct quotation method, where the host currency units are defined in terms of one unit of foreign currency. When the host currency depreciates, more units are required to obtain one unit of foreign currency, leading to a decrease in FDI inflows. Conversely, an appreciation of the host currency leads to increased FDI inflows. Generally, investors prefer to invest in economies with depreciated currencies, as this enhances their purchasing power and market share through exports. However, if depreciation is accompanied by high inflation, the opposite occurs, as the decline in currency value diminishes the value of FDI inflows and stock, discouraging foreign investors. In Pakistan's case, high inflation rates and government borrowings have led to currency depreciation, resulting in reduced FDI inflows. Multinational corporations (MNCs) are hesitant to invest in Pakistan due to the declining value of their assets and prefer to repatriate their subsidiaries rather than reinvest (Akram et al., 2017).

The output further presents the results of an ARDL model that examines the relationships between FDI and various variables,

including Political Stability (PS), Trade Liberalization (TL), and Investment (INVI). The model, selected based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), reveals significant relationships between these variables. The coefficients indicate that a 1% increase in Political Stability leads to a 1.939945% increase in FDI, while a 1% increase in Trade Liberalization results in a 0.100181% increase in FDI. Diagnostic tests such as R-squared and the Durbin-Watson statistic confirm the model's goodness of fit and the absence of autocorrelation. Overall, the results suggest that the ARDL model is appropriate for analyzing the relationships between FDI and its determinants in the dataset (Akram, 2020).

5. CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, this research study investigates the relationship between interest rates and various macroeconomic variables, such as inflation, political stability, foreign direct investment (FDI), exports of goods and services, and economic growth, using data from 1999 to 2023. The ARDL model was employed to estimate both short-run and long-run relationships. The results indicate that FDI, GDP, inflation, and exports of goods and services are positively related to interest rates, while political stability exhibits a negative relationship. Specifically, GDP growth reflects a robust economy, leading to increased demand for credit and consequently higher interest rates. Similarly, FDI inflows enhance the availability of capital, which also contributes to higher interest rates. Political stability, on the other hand, reduces economic uncertainty and is associated with lower interest rates. A stronger performance in exports signifies a healthy economy, thereby driving up interest rates. Conversely, inflation results in higher interest rates as a measure to counteract inflationary pressures.

To promote economic growth and stability, the government should focus on attracting foreign direct investment and encouraging exports, as these factors positively impact interest rates and contribute to overall economic development. Maintaining low and stable inflation rates is essential to avoid the adverse effects of high interest rates. Additionally, fostering political stability is crucial for reducing economic uncertainty and creating a favorable business environment. Efforts should also be made to stimulate GDP growth, as a thriving economy increases credit demand and consequently drives up interest rates. Investing in infrastructure, supporting entrepreneurship, and enhancing education and skills development are key strategies for stimulating economic growth. Furthermore, effective regulation of interest rates is necessary to balance economic expansion with inflation management, ensuring a conducive business environment. By implementing these policies, the government can create a supportive framework for sustained economic growth, development, and stability in Pakistan.

Ethical approval

Not Applicable.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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